

Table S2. The nucleotide diversity (Π) values of 264 homologous loci.

Order	Fragment	Length (bp)	Aligned length (bp)	Nucleotide diversity (Π)	Region
1	<i>trnH-GUG</i>	74	74	0	LSC
2	<i>trnH-GUG-psbA</i>	287-355	362	0.0229643	LSC
3	<i>psbA</i>	1062	1062	0.002772547	LSC
4	<i>psbA-trnK-UUU</i>	255-267	267	0.010893246	LSC
5	<i>3'-trnK-UUU</i>	35	35	0.006349206	LSC
6	<i>3'-trnK-UUU-matK</i>	264-268	270	0.009469697	LSC
7	<i>matK</i>	1506	1506	0.007414785	LSC
8	<i>matK-5'-trnK-UUU</i>	736-748	753	0.006687946	LSC
9	<i>5'-trnK-UUU</i>	37	37	0	LSC
10	<i>5'-trnK-UUU-rps16</i>	799-838	866	0.016594982	LSC
11	<i>rps16 exon2</i>	230	230	0.001932367	LSC
12	<i>rps16 intron</i>	896-907	929	0.009280161	LSC
13	<i>rps16 exon1</i>	40	40	0.005555556	LSC
14	<i>rps16-trnQ-UUG</i>	958-1015	1107	0.011896002	LSC
15	<i>trnQ-UUG</i>	72	72	0	LSC
16	<i>trnQ-UUG-psbK</i>	384-388	388	0.009693287	LSC
17	<i>psbK</i>	186	186	0.004181601	LSC
18	<i>psbK-psbI</i>	234	234	0.00617284	LSC
19	<i>psbI</i>	111	111	0.009009009	LSC
20	<i>psbI-trnS-GCU</i>	57-209	213	0.007936508	LSC
21	<i>trnS-GCU</i>	88	88	0	LSC
22	<i>trnS-GCU-trnG-UCC</i>	548-568	580	0.01135442	LSC
23	<i>5'-trnG-UCC</i>	23	23	0	LSC
24	<i>trnG-UCC intron</i>	697-698	699	0.006057708	LSC
25	<i>3'-trnG-UCC</i>	48	48	0	LSC
26	<i>trnG-UCC-trnR-UCU</i>	187-208	208	0.017973856	LSC
27	<i>trnR-UCU</i>	72	72	0	LSC
28	<i>trnR-UCU-atpA</i>	477-505	512	0.021883754	LSC
29	<i>atpA</i>	1524	1524	0.002661126	LSC
30	<i>atpA-atpF</i>	50	50	0.008888889	LSC
31	<i>atpF</i>	555	555	0.003303303	LSC
32	<i>atpF-atpH</i>	480-485	494	0.008610521	LSC
33	<i>atpH</i>	246	246	0	LSC
34	<i>atpH-atpI</i>	740-747	750	0.006669698	LSC
35	<i>atpI</i>	744	744	0.001941458	LSC
36	<i>atpI-rps2</i>	212-214	214	0.006158281	LSC
37	<i>rps2</i>	711	711	0.003281763	LSC
38	<i>rps2-rpoC2</i>	195-217	218	0.015625	LSC
39	<i>rpoC2</i>	4122-4134	4134	0.003782046	LSC
40	<i>rpoC2-rpoC1</i>	167-176	176	0	LSC
41	<i>rpoC1 exon2</i>	1611	1611	0.001241465	LSC
42	<i>rpoC1 intron</i>	760-770	771	0.006871345	LSC
43	<i>rpoC1 exon1</i>	432	432	0.005529835	LSC
44	<i>rpoC1-rpoB</i>	31	31	0	LSC
45	<i>rpoB</i>	3213	3213	0.002956738	LSC
46	<i>rpoB-trnC-GCA</i>	1038-1072	1081	0.009680542	LSC
47	<i>trnC-GCA</i>	71	71	0	LSC
48	<i>trnC-GCA-petN</i>	771-794	829	0.007126236	LSC
49	<i>petN</i>	90	90	0	LSC
50	<i>petN-psbM</i>	1203-1250	1259	0.007334451	LSC
51	<i>psbM</i>	105-111	111	0.002116402	LSC
52	<i>psbM-trnD-GUC</i>	1012-1044	1065	0.006888889	LSC
53	<i>trnD-GUC</i>	74	74	0.003003003	LSC
54	<i>trnD-GUC-trnY-GUA</i>	361-439	444	0.008114856	LSC
55	<i>trnY-GUA</i>	84	84	0.002645503	LSC
56	<i>trnY-GUA-trnE-UUC</i>	59	59	0.011299435	LSC

57	<i>trnE-UUC</i>	73	73	0	LSC
58	<i>trnE-UUC-trnT-GGU</i>	461-523	565	0.010604965	LSC
59	<i>trnT-GGU</i>	72	72	0	LSC
60	<i>trnT-GGU-psbD</i>	1248-1270	1284	0.008367072	LSC
61	<i>psbD</i>	1062	1062	0.001569366	LSC
62	<i>psbC</i>	1422	1422	0.00167995	LSC
63	<i>psbC-trnS-UGA</i>	247-252	252	0.01897019	LSC
64	<i>trnS-UGA</i>	93	93	0	LSC
65	<i>trnS-UGA-psbZ</i>	381-395	401	0.010490544	LSC
66	<i>psbZ</i>	189	189	0.004703116	LSC
67	<i>psbZ-trnG-GCC</i>	316-365	398	0.012658228	LSC
68	<i>trnG-GCC</i>	71	71	0	LSC
69	<i>trnG-GCC-trnfM-CAU</i>	178-183	183	0.004681648	LSC
70	<i>trnfM-CAU</i>	74	74	0.007507508	LSC
71	<i>trnfM-CAU-rps14</i>	162	162	0	LSC
72	<i>rps14</i>	303	303	0.003667033	LSC
73	<i>rps14-psaB</i>	120-129	129	0.022453704	LSC
74	<i>psaB</i>	2205	2205	0.001637692	LSC
75	<i>psaB-psaA</i>	25	25	0	LSC
76	<i>psaA</i>	2253	2253	0.001775411	LSC
77	<i>psaA-ycf3</i>	725-738	740	0.005378823	LSC
78	<i>ycf3 exon3</i>	153	153	0.001452433	LSC
79	<i>ycf3 intron2</i>	766-793	800	0.004786771	LSC
80	<i>ycf3 exon2</i>	230	230	0.001932367	LSC
81	<i>ycf3 intron1</i>	719-740	749	0.004023522	LSC
82	<i>ycf3 exon1</i>	124	124	0.003584229	LSC
83	<i>ycf3-trnS-GGA</i>	446-891	903	0.023598251	LSC
84	<i>trnS-GGA</i>	87	87	0	LSC
85	<i>trnS-GGA-rps4</i>	294-297	303	0.011574074	LSC
86	<i>rps4</i>	606	606	0.004583792	LSC
87	<i>rps4- trnT-UGU</i>	393-412	421	0.012046485	LSC
88	<i>trnT-UGU</i>	73	73	0	LSC
89	<i>trnT-UGU-trnL-UAA</i>	1058-1093	1183	0.011444335	LSC
90	<i>5'-trnL-UAA</i>	35	35	0	LSC
91	<i>trnL-UAA intron</i>	556-576	576	0.003597122	LSC
92	<i>3'-trnL-UAA</i>	50	50	0.004444444	LSC
93	<i>trnL-UAA-trnF-GAA</i>	392-419	419	0.006695157	LSC
94	<i>trnF-GAA</i>	73	73	0	LSC
95	<i>trnF-GAA-ndhJ</i>	709-819	825	0.010472918	LSC
96	<i>ndhJ</i>	477	477	0.001397624	LSC
97	<i>ndhJ-ndhK</i>	124	124	0.00672043	LSC
98	<i>ndhK</i>	681	681	0.005547398	LSC
99	<i>ndhK-ndhC</i>	44	44	0.008838384	LSC
100	<i>ndhC</i>	363	363	0.005662687	LSC
101	<i>ndhC-trnV-UAC</i>	651-674	730	0.030537459	LSC
102	<i>3'-trnV-UAC</i>	35	35	0	LSC
103	<i>trnV-UAC intron</i>	603	603	0.00285609	LSC
104	<i>5'-trnV-UAC</i>	39	39	0	LSC
105	<i>trnV-UAC-trnM-CAU</i>	161-162	162	0.008971705	LSC
106	<i>trnM-CAU</i>	73	73	0	LSC
107	<i>trnM-CAU-atpE</i>	152-181	181	0.006944444	LSC
108	<i>atpE</i>	402	402	0.004560531	LSC
109	<i>atpE-atpB</i>	22	22	0	LSC
110	<i>atpB</i>	1479	1479	0.001878146	LSC
111	<i>atpB-rbcL</i>	735-749	749	0.006105006	LSC
112	<i>rbcL</i>	1428	1428	0.005582789	LSC
113	<i>rbcL-accD</i>	643-674	689	0.007296062	LSC
114	<i>accD</i>	1461	1461	0.003954673	LSC

115	<i>accD-psaI</i>	443-482	514	0.012503222	LSC
116	<i>psaI</i>	114	114	0.003898635	LSC
117	<i>psaI-ycf4</i>	423-426	426	0.010005266	LSC
118	<i>ycf4</i>	555	555	0.003903904	LSC
119	<i>ycf4-cemA</i>	454-464	472	0.005742821	LSC
120	<i>cemA</i>	690	690	0.002818035	LSC
121	<i>cemA-petA</i>	214	214	0.005970924	LSC
122	<i>petA</i>	963	963	0.001903773	LSC
123	<i>petA-psbJ</i>	842-873	899	0.00914797	LSC
124	<i>psbJ</i>	123	123	0.004516712	LSC
125	<i>psbJ-psbL</i>	139-163	165	0.008856683	LSC
126	<i>psbL</i>	117	117	0.001899335	LSC
127	<i>psbL-psbF</i>	22	22	0.01010101	LSC
128	<i>psbF</i>	120	120	0	LSC
129	<i>psbF-psbE</i>	9	9	0	LSC
130	<i>psbE</i>	252	252	0.003968254	LSC
131	<i>psbE-petL</i>	1192-1236	1260	0.00745429	LSC
132	<i>petL</i>	96	96	0.009259259	LSC
133	<i>petL-petG</i>	169-170	170	0.006574622	LSC
134	<i>petG</i>	114	114	0	LSC
135	<i>petG-trnW-CCA</i>	123	123	0.005420054	LSC
136	<i>trnW-CCA</i>	74	74	0.003003003	LSC
137	<i>trnW-CCA-trnP-UGG</i>	144-149	150	0.007330247	LSC
138	<i>trnP-UGG</i>	74	74	0	LSC
139	<i>trnP-UGG-psaJ</i>	424-444	444	0.005110063	LSC
140	<i>psaJ</i>	135	135	0.001646091	LSC
141	<i>psaJ-rpl33</i>	354-478	479	0.013212353	LSC
142	<i>rpl33</i>	201	201	0.002211166	LSC
143	<i>rpl33-rps18</i>	191	191	0.001163467	LSC
144	<i>rps18</i>	306	306	0.000726216	LSC
145	<i>rps18-rpl20</i>	280-298	298	0.006571087	LSC
146	<i>rpl20</i>	354	354	0.001883239	LSC
147	<i>rpl20-5'-rps12</i>	770-776	777	0.009704185	LSC
148	<i>5'-rps12</i>	114	114	0.001949318	LSC
149	<i>5'-rps12-clpP</i>	180-189	196	0.008024691	LSC
150	<i>clpP</i> exon3	228	228	0.002923977	LSC
151	<i>clpP</i> intron2	656-664	670	0.007211128	LSC
152	<i>clpP</i> exon2	292	292	0.003805175	LSC
153	<i>clpP</i> intron1	818-957	967	0.00604782	LSC
154	<i>clpP</i> exon1	71	71	0.00312989	LSC
155	<i>clpP-psbB</i>	432-435	435	0.006687243	LSC
156	<i>psbB</i>	1527	1527	0.002073783	LSC
157	<i>psbB-psbT</i>	190	190	0.004678363	LSC
158	<i>psbT</i>	102	102	0	LSC
159	<i>psbT-psbN</i>	66	66	0.01010101	LSC
160	<i>psbN</i>	132	132	0.001683502	LSC
161	<i>psbN-psbH</i>	118	118	0.005178908	LSC
162	<i>psbH</i>	225	225	0.004691358	LSC
163	<i>psbH-petB</i>	123	123	0.008130081	LSC
164	<i>petB</i> exon1	6	6	0	LSC
165	<i>petB</i> intron	768-784	792	0.008178603	LSC
166	<i>petB</i> exon2	642	642	0.001384562	LSC
167	<i>petB-petD</i>	210-221	221	0.002116402	LSC
168	<i>petD</i> exon1	8	8	0	LSC
169	<i>petD</i> intron	723-751	752	0.006800369	LSC
170	<i>petD</i> exon2	475	475	0.001403509	LSC
171	<i>petD-rpoA</i>	205-213	213	0.01430143	LSC
172	<i>rpoA</i>	996	996	0.001561803	LSC

173	<i>rpoA-rps11</i>	59	59	0	LSC
174	<i>rps11</i>	417	417	0.003730349	LSC
175	<i>rps11-rpl36</i>	143-149	149	0.006216006	LSC
176	<i>rpl36</i>	114	114	0.005847953	LSC
177	<i>rpl36-rps8</i>	301-308	308	0.011997047	LSC
178	<i>rps8</i>	405	405	0.002194787	LSC
179	<i>rps8-rpl14</i>	179-230	233	0.006828057	LSC
180	<i>rpl14</i>	318-369	369	0.002445842	LSC
181	<i>rpl14-rpl16</i>	134-155	157	0.005089059	LSC
182	<i>rpl16</i> exon2	399	399	0.004873294	LSC
183	<i>rpl16</i> intron	956-1033	1060	0.006626435	LSC
184	<i>rpl16</i> exon1	9	9	0	LSC
185	<i>rpl16-rps3</i>	104-107	107	0	LSC
186	<i>rps3</i>	657	657	0.003720616	LSC
187	<i>rps3-rpl22</i>	130-152	156	0.015384615	LSC
188	<i>rpl22</i>	408-420	420	0.01416122	LSC
189	<i>rpl22-rps19</i>	92-141	142	0.039506173	LSC
190	<i>rps19</i>	279	279	0.006371963	LSC
191	<i>rps19-rpl2</i>	60-74	74	0.035185185	LSC/IR
192	<i>rpl2</i> exon2	434	434	0.000896057	IR
193	<i>rpl2</i> intron	673	673	0.000330196	IR
194	<i>rpl2</i> exon1	391	391	0.000568343	IR
195	<i>rpl2-rpl23</i>	18	18	0	IR
196	<i>rpl23</i>	282	282	0	IR
197	<i>rpl23-trnI-CAU</i>	165-185	185	0	IR
198	<i>trnI-CAU</i>	74	74	0	IR
199	<i>trnI-CAU-ycf2</i>	88	88	0	IR
200	<i>ycf2</i>	6822-6828	6828	0.000912885	IR
201	<i>ycf2-trnL-CAA</i>	507-514	514	0.000438308	IR
202	<i>trnL-CAA</i>	81	81	0	IR
203	<i>trnL-CAA-ndhB</i>	494	494	0.000449843	IR
204	<i>ndhB</i> exon2	756	756	0.000293945	IR
205	<i>ndhB</i> intron	676-682	682	0.001150559	IR
206	<i>ndhB</i> exon1	777	777	0	IR
207	<i>ndhB-rps7</i>	321	321	0	IR
208	<i>rps7</i>	468	468	0	IR
209	<i>rps7-3'-rps12</i>	52	52	0	IR
210	<i>3'-rps12</i> exon3	26	26	0	IR
211	<i>3'-rps12</i> intron	543	543	0	IR
212	<i>3'-rps12</i> exon2	232	232	0	IR
213	<i>3'-rps12-trnV-GAC</i>	1703-1718	1723	0.001565864	IR
214	<i>trnV-GAC</i>	72	72	0	IR
215	<i>trnV-GAC-rrn16</i>	218	218	0.002038736	IR
216	<i>rrn16</i>	1491	1491	0.000260824	IR
217	<i>rrn16-trnI-GAU</i>	297	297	0.003741115	IR
218	<i>5'-trnI-GAU</i>	37	37	0	IR
219	<i>trnI-GAU</i> intron	954-955	955	0.000465875	IR
220	<i>3'-trnI-GAU</i>	35	35	0	IR
221	<i>trnI-GAU-trnA-UGC</i>	64	64	0	IR
222	<i>5'-trnA-UGC</i>	38	38	0	IR
223	<i>trnA-UGC</i> intron	811-814	814	0.00082203	IR
224	<i>3'-trnA-UGC</i>	35	35	0	IR
225	<i>trnA-UGC-rrn23</i>	162	162	0.007544582	IR
226	<i>rrn23</i>	2809	2809	0.000494442	IR
227	<i>rrn23-rrn4.5</i>	98	98	0	IR
228	<i>rrn4.5</i>	103	103	0	IR
229	<i>rrn4.5-rrn5</i>	253	253	0.000878349	IR
230	<i>rrn5</i>	121	121	0	IR

231	<i>rrn5-trnR-ACG</i>	257-259	259	0.003458712	IR
232	<i>trnR-ACG</i>	74	74	0	IR
233	<i>trnR-ACG-trnN-GUU</i>	454-468	468	0.007097406	IR
234	<i>trnN-GUU</i>	72	72	0	IR
235	<i>trnN-GUU-ψycf1</i>	326	326	0	IR
236	<i>ψycf1</i>	1110-1203	1233	0.000763126	IR/SSC
237	<i>ψycf1-ndhF</i>	61-315	323	0.061550152	SSC
238	<i>ndhF</i>	2244-2256	2256	0.006399782	SSC
239	<i>ndhF-rpl32</i>	1102-1176	1193	0.00896884	SSC
240	<i>rpl32</i>	159	159	0.00698812	SSC
241	<i>rpl32-trnL-UAG</i>	640-675	678	0.007892901	SSC
242	<i>trnL-UAG</i>	80	80	0	SSC
243	<i>trnL-UAG-ccsA</i>	85-86	86	0.020261438	SSC
244	<i>ccsA</i>	966	966	0.005060962	SSC
245	<i>ccsA-ndhD</i>	279-323	367	0.027896486	SSC
246	<i>ndhD</i>	1497-1500	1500	0.007459363	SSC
247	<i>ndhD-psaC</i>	115-123	123	0.00531401	SSC
248	<i>psaC</i>	246	246	0.000903342	SSC
249	<i>psaC-ndhE</i>	242-252	252	0.008838384	SSC
250	<i>ndhE</i>	303-306	306	0.00220022	SSC
251	<i>ndhE-ndhG</i>	249-271	272	0.011713521	SSC
252	<i>ndhG</i>	531	531	0.004184976	SSC
253	<i>ndhG-ndhI</i>	390-398	398	0.009900285	SSC
254	<i>ndhI</i>	504	504	0.000440917	SSC
255	<i>ndhI-ndhA</i>	75	75	0.011851852	SSC
256	<i>ndhA exon2</i>	539	539	0.004638219	SSC
257	<i>ndhA intron</i>	1185-1237	1260	0.009947768	SSC
258	<i>ndhA exon1</i>	553	553	0.003013864	SSC
259	<i>ndhA-ndhH</i>	1	1	0	SSC
260	<i>ndhH</i>	1182	1182	0.002914082	SSC
261	<i>ndhH-rps15</i>	103-107	107	0.006472492	SSC
262	<i>rps15</i>	273	273	0.001628002	SSC
263	<i>rps15-ycf1</i>	400-419	435	0.017405513	SSC
264	<i>ycf1</i>	5688-5751	5824	0.008550046	SSC/IR